

The State and the Politics

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Political action aims to maximize the compatibility between means and ends. What is wanted is to rationalize the destination and application of Power, employing norms and methods that subordinate the pursuit of effectiveness to ethical precepts.

Politics is a natural fact of human coexistence. The earliest evidence of man's presence on earth already shows him living in groups because of his safety.

It is up to society, through Politics, to establish social objectives to compose a social order, to distinguish the public from the private sector, to structure the State, and to guarantee individual rights.

These are tasks assigned primarily to the politician, who must have solid axiological foundations, a clear vision of the future, and be identified with the interests of the Nation.

The decisions made in this plan are lasting and shape the fate of society as a whole.

In a more action-oriented plan, it is up to the Policy:

- To gather wills around objectives;
- Seek consensus, support for administrative action;
- Allocating resources to the different sectors of the State and
- Defining guidelines, according a national project.

Politics considers the international level, where the Government of one country must live with governments of other equally sovereign countries. The great goals of each Nation, however, even when conflicting, remain unchanged.

Politics and Power are issues linked to the problem of Power, in which many authors focus on the very foundation of politics.

Several schools of thought seek an understanding of them. Sociologically, Power is the ability or authority to lead men, leading them to obedience or compelling them to act in a certain way.

From the juridical point of view, Power is the basis of all political organizations, and, in this sense, it is linked to the concept of State - organized Power to govern the Nation politically.

The formation of the State coincides precisely with the monopoly of the use of Power, and authority because it has the coercibility, that is, the ability to obey, through legal instruments.

There is a relationship between political actions and ethical requirements because those actions must be guided by the values that inspire social life, arising from the cultural matrix.

Individual ethics and political ethics must coexist. The first is an ethic of conviction. The second, it is the ethics of results.

This statement does not authorize the generalization of the formula that the ends justify the means, nor the fast conclusion that it is parallel and independent axiology.

The practical exercise of the art of politics must require reconciling the values that should guide man's personal decisions, with those that focused on the Common Good.

The analysis of a nation's historical and cultural process allows us to identify the decisions with which it marks its destiny.

It is usual for the Government, seeking to situate itself as an interpreter of the will of the people, to set objectives that respond clearly and appropriately to national aspirations. Disagreement will favour the outbreak of crises.

The continuity of certain coherent positions throughout the Nation's historical-cultural process expresses a definition of objectives whose set is National Policy itself.

The study of successive Government Policies is, therefore, an essential subsidy for the understanding of National Policy. A right National Policy emerges when one seeks to rationally apply the National Power, orienting it towards the Common Good.

There are two fundamental aspects to consider in the analysis of this Policy:

- The National Objectives to be achieved and preserved, and
- The National Power to be employed for such purpose.

National Policy is characterized by its broad scope over time, as it identifies with the Fundamental Objectives and must be understood through the set of successive Government Policies.

The National Policy, taken as a reference for significant State decisions, should include Defense and Development objectives centred on the desire for preservation or evolution, whether in the internal or external fields.

Since the Government directs the State by the delegation of the Nation, the Government Policy is contained in the National Policy and should be consistent with it.

A Policy proposes the attainment and maintenance of Fundamental Objectives, without worrying about the capacity of the National Power or the existence of obstacles that impede its use.

The National Policy is divided into defined periods that may be realized in the form of Government Objectives.

Government Policy thus represents a step down the scale of political dynamics and develops in terms delimited by the motivations and circumstances of the conjuncture.

On the other hand, it serves as a reference for the efforts of society as a whole, influencing the autonomous decisions of its different segments or component groups, because of the objectives they seek to achieve.

National Power. Therefore, the split into two major fields, Security and Development, from which Sector, Regional, and Specific Policies can be derived, is justified.

1 - Internal Policy and Foreign Policy The development in Internal and Foreign Policy is justified by the need to highlight the peculiarities, especially the limitations of the State's actions, both internally and externally, due to the double condition of the maximum entity in the internal field of an entity that must coexist, with equal rights, with other nations in the international sphere.

The foreign and domestic policies of the countries interpenetrate and are mutually dependent.

2 - Policies refer to the activities specific to the various segments into which public administration is divided (transport, communications, agriculture, education, health, and others).

In a State, the planning and implementation of sectoral actions should not do without close coordination and cooperation between the various levels of Government. Regional Policies have a spatial approach, involving the joint effort, within a given geographical area, of multiple organs and entities generally under specific central coordination.

Specific or Special Policies are adopted for the set of activities considered by a particular Government to be high relevance.

The art of governing becomes increasingly difficult and complicated. Pure persuasion is not enough, for reaching consensus on results does not always mean participation, and the value of leadership and the prestige of authority are often insufficient to overcome specific resistances. Decisive action must be taken against the obstacles that

stand before national interests, which is represented by continuous and pertinent effort until the desired end is achieved. And this occurs both at the National and International levels.

Overcoming the obstacles that hinder or hinder the achievement and maintenance of the Objectives, therefore, requires the preparation and proper use of the Power, in a specific form of struggle.

This struggle or effort of the Nation is what is characterized as Strategy, and may require the concurrence of elements from multiple sectors of society.

The Strategy is the art of preparing and applying the Power to achieve and preserve objectives, overcoming obstacles of every order.

The National Power is not applied in a vacuum, and the similarity of energy changes in the process of its application, because the social environment that acts is not neutral.

Thus, it is natural that, in human society, there are and multiply obstacles that prevent or totally or partially hinder the use of Power to achieve the desired results.

Constraints of every order prevent the achievement and maintenance of objectives. These obstacles, existing or potential, may or may not be material. They sometimes result from natural phenomena, such as droughts and floods, sometimes from social factors such as hunger, poverty, and illiteracy, or even from the human will.

Sometimes they represent, in their essence, structural conditions, and may also vary in intensity and in the way they manifest themselves. Obstacles are classified into adverse factors and antagonisms.

Adverse factors are obstacles that stand in the form of society or government efforts to achieve and preserve the National Objectives. When obstacles become detrimental to society's efforts to make the Fundamental Goals, they are called Antagonisms. Antagonisms are obstacles of all kinds, internal or external, which oppose the achievement and preservation of the Fundamental Objectives.

Social relations are marked by constant clashes of interests that generate imbalances, sometimes requiring actions necessary to restore the equilibrium.

This phenomenon affects the relationships between individuals between social groups and between nations. Thus, sociologically, a clash of interests of any kind is understood as conflict.

Depending on its magnitude, conflict can also constitute an obstacle to the use of Power. When it comes to the use of National Power in the achievement and

preservation of National Objectives, obstacles of this origin must be carefully studied. This understanding leads to the need to know the nature, causes, and actors involved in conflicts so that we can eliminate or minimize their effects. Otherwise, when the conflict provoked by factors internal and external to its environment worsens, it reaches a state of tension that we call a crisis. At this stage, the conflict, if not adequately managed, risks aggravation to the point of confrontation or confrontation of the parties or actors involved. The crisis is, therefore, reversible, and the conflict that generates it is not always. A crisis is a state of tension, caused by internal and/or external factors, under which a clash of interests, if not correctly managed, risks being aggravated to the point of confrontation between the parties involved. When formulating government policies, latent crises, whether internal or external, must be considered. Managing them is government duty.

National Strategy is the art of preparing and applying National Power to, overcoming the obstacles, achieving and preserving the National Objectives, following the guidelines established by the National Policy.

The National Strategy draws the political, economic, psychosocial, military, and scientific-technological means that make up the National Power.

There are no means whose use is promoting evolution (Development) or only ensuring preservation (Security). The National Strategy is concerned with the achievement of objectives aimed equally at Security and Development.

The perfect coordination and the right adjustment between Policy and Strategy are essential. Policy and Strategy need to be coordinated and adjusted at all junctures, levels, and areas of action and should be harmonized with each other and with the real needs and availability of resources as a fundamental condition for achieving the desired successes.

Many plans and programs fail to meet this condition. By identifying and defining objectives, politics guides the destinies of society, organizing the social order and the State, distinguishing between the public and private sectors, and ensuring individual rights.

It is fundamentally concerned with the evolution and survival of the Nation, seeking to meet national interests and aspirations.

It takes care of the National Power, managing public goods, and protecting private assets; promotes the enhancement and strengthening of Power, and ensures its balance.

The fixed references of politics are justice and ethics, without which the social order is destroyed, and the Nation itself disintegrates. Thus, the Policy will indicate what to do.

The Strategy involves a form of struggle that employs the means of Power to overcome all obstacles to the best interests of society.

In this sense, its permanent guideline is its effectiveness, that is, its commitment to the achievement of the objectives set by the Policy, without neglecting, however, the efficiency, that is, of obtaining the maximum yield from the available means.

How to employ Power, the how-to-do, which is characteristic of the Strategy, has its field of action limited by a political orientation that subordinates the strategic principle of effectiveness to the ethical postulates of Politics.

In turn, the Policy must know the needs of the Strategy. When the means are inadequate or inadequate, it is the Policy to guide other factors or to formulate more modest objectives.

At the government level, the three essential elements of the Strategy are also considered:

- The means,
- The obstacles, and
- The aims to be achieved.

From the interrelationship of these elements is regarded as the guidelines established by the Government Policy regarding the deadlines and priorities for the application of the means, the most appropriate Strategies will be found to achieve and maintain the respective Goals.

Government Strategy is the way the Government prepares and applies the National Power to, overcoming the obstacles, deliver and preserve its Goals, according to the guidelines established by the Government Policy. The means must be applied at the right time, in the exact amount and place where they can best produce the desired effects.

Given the understanding of the concept of Government Strategy, there are indeed developments in a set of strategies that materialize, in time and space, the National Strategy. Such events are established according to:

- The nature of existing or potential obstacles and also the predominance of the aspirations for evolution or preservation contained in the Government Objectives; and
- The current and future preparation and application needs of the National Power, with emphasis on one or more of its expressions, taking into account the predominance of the nature of the means, the level of coverage, and the desired effects.

Strategies will be Sectoral, Regional, and Specific.

National Power is the instrument used by the Nation to achieve and preserve the National Objectives through policies and strategies.

Actions characterize the Government Strategy.

Strategic Actions are the realization of the use of Power in Strategic Areas.

Strategic Actions of any kind can be carried out both in geographical areas and in different areas of human activity.

Strategic Areas are spaces of any nature, characterized by the presence or the possibility of the existence of relevant interests or significant obstacles to the achievement of the Policy.

- Development must be understood as a global social process, in which all structures undergo continuous and profound evolutionary transformations, that is, always recognized as National Development.

Man's Development must be understood as a process of permanent improvement of his physical, spiritual, intellectual, and moral attributes.

The Development securing and strengthening the physical base of the Nation results not only from the implementation of policies and strategies for the rational and productive use of the internal areas of the national territory but also from the evolution of the National Power in all its Expressions.

Signify steps towards the Common Good.

The Development of the institutions is mainly portrayed in the improvement and functioning of the political, economic, social, military, and scientific-technological institutions, enabling continuity in the overall process of National Development itself.

Development and the global process of human enhancement, land strengthening - the Nation's fixed base - and social system improvements.

National Development should not be confused with the Nation's economic growth. It is an indispensable factor of the process, but it does not involve the sense of comprehensiveness and the ethical content of the former. It is fundamentally a process of change where, more than ever, the technique resides in the valorization of man.

The exactly dimension of National Development is not in the indicator numbers of the breadth of material growth, but in the transformations that society can make to

approach the ideal of the Common Good. It is a process identified with the pursuit of quality, although many of its aspects can be presented quantitatively.

Development is global, reflecting the concern to rescue values such as the pre-eminence of the person and social justice.

Each Government has its views on how best to use Power to ensure Development. Likewise, each Government sets its objectives, which, in its opinion, contribute to the achievement of the Fundamental Objectives.

The formulation of these policies must involve not only the establishment of goals that reflect the yearnings for evolution, but also the need, imposed by Development itself, to strengthen and perfect National Power.

Sectoral, Regional, or Specific Policies linked to Development impose goals and attitudes on the management bodies and public companies and serve as a starting point for the preparation of the various plans and programs to be implemented.

On the other hand, considering the democratic character of the State, these Policies serve only as inducers or guidance for private initiative. In any case, to be effective, Sector Policies must have the following characteristics:

- Representativeness;
- Realism;
- Authenticity;
- Compatibility;
- humanistic sense;
- Flexibility.

Representativeness It is the sense of participation of all in the development effort. The legitimacy of the Government, advantage of the democratic regime, is not enough to conduct the development process.

Government policies must be realistic to avoid frustrations and disappointments. The capacity of Power is one of the essential references for the establishment of the Goals of Government. For this reason, the Development process aims to strengthen and perfect the National Power to achieve those goals.

Authenticity Copying models and objectives that are detached from national aspirations is a severe mistake in the formulation of Sectoral Policies.

The media, particularly the mass media, exert different psychological pressures on the national environment, creating needs and aspirations related to particular welfare standards.

Other times, by their characteristics and various stages of Development, they orient their policies according to their specific conditions and cannot, therefore, serve as a model.

Thus, the objectives contained in the Sectoral Policies must be genuinely national, thus maintaining respect and consistency with national traditions and character.

The various Sector Policies must have their origin in Government Policy, as a way of guaranteeing the effectiveness of government actions. On the other hand, although they deal with different sectors of public life, they need to be compatible with each other and must contribute to the achievement of the Goals of Government.

Humanistic Sense Development must have as its reference to increase welfare and social justice. Some Sectoral Policies, notably in developing countries, require a certain degree of concentration of resources to enable the generation of wealth, which opposes the need to share them. In the meantime, the Government must strive to maintain the indispensable balance between resource allocation and concentration as a means of ensuring at the same time, the pace of development and the fulfilment of society's longings.

The dynamism of a continually evolving conjuncture, both internally and externally, may determine the need to reorient the Sectoral Policies or even to alter the various objectives to be achieved.

The analysis of the conjuncture, before the formulation of these policies, implies the need for as perfect estimates as possible.

However, regulation with new data and natural monitoring of the effectiveness of government policies may indicate necessary modifications.

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